

Analysis of Liquid Cooling System for Lithium-Ion Battery Pack using ANSYS

Gautam Varsani¹, Mihir Rameshkumar Vasavada², H.N Raval³, Chirag K Vibhakar⁴

1,2,3,- Department of Electrical Engineering, L. D. College of Engineering, Navrangpura, Ahmedabad - 380015, Gujarat India. 4 - Gujarat Power Engineering and Research Institute (constituent college of GTU), Mehsana.

Abstract:- For Electric Vehicle Battery pack it is necessary to increase performance and lifespan due to the rising demand for electric vehicles (EVs). Since too much heat can result in reduced efficiency, safety risks, and accelerated battery cell degradation, effective thermal management is essential. In this study we had conducted the Simulation and analysis of Proposed Serpentine Liquid Cooling Channel Model with different Coolant and channel Materials to Optimize lithium-ion battery packs. A serpentine liquid cooling channel created especially for a 18650 size NMC grade and total 96 Cylindrical lithium-ion cell battery pack is presented in this study. ANSYS software is being used for simulation in this study. To maintain ideal operating temperatures, the suggested cooling system uses liquid cooling techniques. It is possible to assess the battery pack's thermal behavior under varied operating conditions by using computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations. Analysis is done on key performance metrics like cooling efficiency, heat dissipation rates, and temperature distribution. The outcomes show how well the integrated cooling system reduces hot spots and maintains a consistent temperature distribution throughout the battery cells.

Keywords: Lithium-ion batteries, liquid cooling, Serpentine channel.

I. INTRODUCTION:

Conventional fuel-powered vehicles are a significant contributor to nature and air pollution [1]. The rising popularity of new energy vehicles is driven by their energy efficiency and reduced environmental pollution. New energy vehicles mainly consist of electric models that depend exclusively on batteries for power [2–4]. Numerous researchers have carried out studies on electric vehicle batteries. Modern high-power electronic systems, battery thermal management, and industrial heat exchangers all depend on effective thermal management. Excessive heat buildup can cause vital components to fail, perform worse, and have a shorter lifespan. Liquid cooling has become one of the most successful cooling methods available, providing better heat dissipation than air cooling. Serpentine flow channels have drawn a lot of interest in liquid cooling systems because of their improved thermal uniformity, compact design, and improved heat transfer properties for Lithium-ion battery pack.

Heat generation is an inevitable by product of LIB charge and discharge operations, LIB usually perform best within a temperature range of 25 to 40 degrees Celsius. Every lithium-ion battery should function effectively within the appropriate temperature range. Two straightforward indicator thermal non-uniformity and maximum temperature are introduced to make evaluating the BTMS easier. The latter is represented by the temperature differential across LIB pack. The main focus of the current work is temperature nonuniformity, which is absent, will result in variations

in the LIBs' ohmic resistance, current unevenness and nonuniform heat generation. Consequently, maintaining the battery pack's thermal uniformity is crucial to its functionality [5]. A water-Al₂O₃ nanofluid was employed in a novel method by [6], where the 18650-type cell battery pack was immersed in an aluminum cylindrical tank containing nanofluid.

The fluid received the energy produced by the battery pack directly, and air eventually flowed over the tank's surface to remove it. Alternative approaches focus on flow path design with the primary aim of optimizing the cooling system. A number of variables, such as coolant selection, channel geometry, and material composition, affect serpentine liquid channel performance. Variations in thermal conductivity, specific heat capacity, and viscosity among coolants are important factors in determining heat dissipation efficiency. The effects of common coolants on thermal performance, including water, ethylene glycol, and nanofluids, have been extensively researched. Furthermore, the choice of channel materials—such as copper, aluminum, and composite alloys—affects the cooling system's overall durability, mechanical strength, and heat conduction.

The thermal and fluid flow behavior of serpentine liquid channels for various coolant types and channel materials are analyzed and compared in this study using Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations with ANSYS Fluent. The following are the main goals of this study:

- 1) To assess how various coolants affect the serpentine channel's temperature distribution, pressure drop, and heat transfer efficiency.
- 2) To examine the effects of various channel materials on thermal resistance and heat dissipation.
- 3) To find the ideal coolant and channel material combination for optimal cooling efficiency in order to optimize the serpentine channel design.

This study intends to offer important insights into optimizing serpentine cooling channels for enhanced thermal performance and energy efficiency by examining the interaction between coolant properties and channel materials. The results can be used as a basis for developing next-generation liquid cooling systems that improve operational efficiency and dependability in a range of engineering applications.

II. METHODOLOGY FOR SIMULATION STUDY AND EVALUATION.

2.1 Heat Transfer Mode

Conduction: Transfer of heat through direct contact of solid

Convection: Transfer of heat through the movement of Liquid

Radiation: Transfer of heat through electromagnetic waves without Medium

For Battery Pack Cooling with Channel Both Conduction and Convection heat transfer method is required. The goal is to suggest ways to reduce uneven heating in the battery pack by improving cooling using liquid flow through channels. In steady conditions, the channel walls do not significantly impact the heat balance. Also, because the battery pack is well insulated from the outside, the coolant absorbs all the

heat produced by the LIB. Therefore, Newton's law of cooling can be applied.

$$Q = h \cdot A \cdot (T_b - T_c) \quad (1) \quad [7]$$

The primary modes of heat transfer are convection between the coolant and the inner wall of the channel, and conduction between the outer wall of the channel and the LIB.

Here in Eq.1 h represents the equivalent heat transfer coefficient, T_b is the temperature of battery, and Q represents the heat released by the battery pack to the cooling system, T_c is the temperature of the coolant, and A is the contact area between the lithium-ion batteries and the outer wall of the channel. [8]. It should be mentioned that cooling unevenness may result from the coolant temperature rising streamwise.

2.2 Rate of LIB heat generation during simulation

The heat generation rate (Q_{gen}) can be calculated using the following formula.: [8]

$$Q_{gen} = Q_{ir} + Q_{re} = \pm \left[I(U_{ca} - U_{an} - U) - IT \frac{d(U_{ca} - U_{an})}{dT} \right] \quad (2)$$

Q_{ir} = Heat that cannot be reversed, and Q_{re} = Heat that can be reversed heat, are the two factors that affect a Li-i cell's energy generation rate during charging and discharging operations. Here T = temperature of LiB, I = current, U = terminal voltage, U_{ca} and U_{an} = open circuit potentials (OCP) of the neg(-ve) and pos(+ve) electrodes, and The OCP's derivative with regard to temperature is dU/dT .

III. 3D MODELLING STEPS, SIMULATION PRINCIPLE & ITS PROPERTIES

Figure 1: 3D model of Serpentine Channel

Figure 2: 3D Serpentine Channel With 18650 NMC Cell Assembly for Simulation.

The sample prepared for simulation is a 3D Serpentine Channel measuring having 2000mm Length, 60mm Height and thickness of channel is 3 mm as illustrated

in Fig. 1. In Fig 2 total 96 Cells NMC 18650 Type are arranged in systematic Manner. And the Plate Material and Coolant Material are mentioned in Table 1.

Table 1: Different Cases for Cooling Channel

Case	Aluminum Alloy 6016	Case	Copper Alloy C110	Inlet Velocity	At Temperature
A	AA with Water	G	CA with Water	1m/s	313K
B	AA with Ethylene Glycol	H	CA with Ethylene Glycol		
C	AA with Water	I	CA with Water	3m/s	
D	AA with Ethylene Glycol	J	CA with Ethylene Glycol		
E	AA with Water	K	CA with Water	5m/s	
F	AA with Ethylene Glycol	L	CA with Ethylene Glycol		

Table 2: Material Properties [9] [10][11]

Material / Properties	Units	Aluminium Alloy 6016	Copper Alloy C110
Conductivity	(W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	160	385
Specific heat	(J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	900	395
Density	(kg m ⁻³)	2700	8930
Melting Point	(K)	858	1356

Table 3: Coolant Properties [11]

Coolant Material / Properties	Units	Water	Water 50% + Ethylene Glycol 50%

Coolant viscosity	(Pas)	0.00089	0.0042
Coolant Conductivity	(W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	0.606	0.40
Coolant Specific Heat	(J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	4182	3300
Coolant Density	(kg m ⁻³)	997	1080
Boiling Point	(K)	373	385
Freezing Point	(K)	273	239

Steps :

1. In this simulation a three-dimensional model was introduced and the geometry module of DS SolidWorks software is used to create the 3D model of the cooling channel and LIB pack. At the time of model designing all the dimensions of the model are marked. The channel wall is 1 mm thick, and the cooling plate is 3 mm thick and length of 2000 mm. Total 96 cell of 18650

Type are Considered. Arrangement of cell are 8 in Series and 12 in parallel System. To guarantee a smooth subsequent simulation, the coolant inlet and outlet of a serpentine channel are clearly illustrated in Figure 1 [13] [14].

2. After that, imports the 3D model in ANSYS to create the model mesh. Access the Mesh module and choose the tetrahedral mesh type. The mesh division results in a total element of 632637 units, with element size 300 mm as the. The meshing result is illustrated in Figure 3.

3. Next step is to establish the boundaries. Setting the boundary conditions comes next after meshing is completed. First, adjust the coolant's water velocity to 1 m/s and set the inlet water temperature to 300 K. The configuration of the heat source is the most important boundary condition. Here, the lithium battery pack is considered as a uniform body heat source. In this simulation, 96 lithium cells are simulated and consider as a source of heat. The following assumptions are also considered [14]: 1) Internal convection and thermal radiation within the battery are ignored. 2) The heat capacity of the battery is constant and does not vary over time. 3) The battery is isotropic.

The coolant flow is identified as turbulent based on the Reynolds number. The precise calculation formula is as follows [14]:

$$Re = \frac{\rho v d}{\mu} \quad (3)$$

The formula uses d as a characteristic length and v is velocity of fluid, ρ is density, and μ is coefficients of viscosity respectively. Following computation, it is

discovered that the channel has a turbulent flow with a Reynolds number greater than 4000.

In the simulation, thermal energy from the battery pack is transferred to the cooling plate through direct contact. Thermal conduction facilitates the transfer of heat between the battery pack and the cooling plate. The energy balance equation for the battery pack is [15]:

$$\rho C \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = k \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} \right) + Q \quad (4)$$

where ρ represent the density, C represent the heat capacity, and T represent the temperature of the LIB, k is the thermal conductivity and heat generation rate is denoted by Q.

The energy balance equation for the cooling plate can be expressed as [15]:

$$\rho_p C_p \frac{\partial T_p}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot (k_p \nabla T_p) \quad (5)$$

ρ_p , C_p , T_p , and k_p represent the cooling plate's density, heat capacity, temperature, and thermal conductivity, r espectively.

The convective heat transfer equation [15] applies to the lithium batteries exterior surface and the surrounding air.

$$q = h(T - T_0) \quad (6)$$

where q expresses the heat generation rate per unit volume, h denotes the convective heat transfer coefficient, and T_0 represent the ambient temperature.

The energy conservation equation for the coolant (water) can be written as follows: [15].

$$\rho_c C_c \frac{\partial T_c}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_c C_c v T_c) = \nabla \cdot (k_c \nabla T_c) \quad (7)$$

where ρ_c denote mass density, C_c denotes heat capacity, T_c denotes temperature, k_c denotes thermal conductivity, and v indicate the velocity of the coolant (water) in m/s, respectively.

The continuity equation is expressed as follows: [15]

$$\frac{\partial \rho_c}{\partial t} + \nabla(\rho_c v) = 0 \quad (8)$$

Here the fluid is taken as an incompressible and its density is constant, equation (8) can be written into:

$$\nabla(v) = 0$$

The momentum equation for the coolant (water) is expressed as [15]:

$$\rho_c \frac{dv}{dt} = -\nabla P + \mu \nabla^2 v \quad (9)$$

P denotes static pressure and μ denotes dynamic viscosity of coolant in eq (9).

The thermal performance of a 96-cell lithium-ion battery pack integrated with an active liquid cooling system utilizing water as the coolant was numerically analyzed using ANSYS CFD simulations. The cooling channel, constructed from aluminum alloy 6016 and other from Copper Alloy C110, was designed to maintain efficient heat dissipation under operational conditions, with an inlet velocity of 1,3,5 m/s with water and water + Ethylene glycol 1:1 Simulation time is considered as 10 minute coolant flow . The objective was to evaluate temperature distribution, thermal gradients, and cooling efficiency within the battery pack. Different cases results are conducted. Total 12 Cases are considered and compared. In this Simulation 10 Temperature points data are collected at every 1 minutes which are plotted on graphs.

Figure 3: Mesh Model of Whole Assembly in Ansys.

IV. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS:

4.1 CASE A: AA with Water at inlet velocity of 1m/s at 313 K.

The simulation results in Figure 4 indicate a distinct thermal gradient along the coolant flow direction, with temperatures ranging from 313 K to 311 K. As observed from the contour plot, cells near the inlet region exhibit lower temperatures (~311 K). The increasing temperature along the coolant path can be attributed to progressive heat absorption by the water coolant as it flows through the channel.

Each individual cell demonstrates a radial temperature gradient, with higher temperatures concentrated at the core due to localized Joule heating and electrochemical reactions. The outer periphery of the cells remains relatively cooler, suggesting effective convective heat dissipation facilitated by the cooling channel.

However, cells positioned centrally within the pack exhibit higher thermal accumulation, which could potentially lead to thermal non-uniformity and localized hotspots during prolonged operation.

Figure 4: AA Channel with water as coolant at 1m/s

Figure 5: Cooling Curve of Cell with water at 1m/s

.As from figure 6 the water-based active cooling system Curve demonstrates effective thermal regulation, maintaining a temperature differential of approximately ~2 K across the battery pack .

4.2 CASE B: AA with Water 50% + Ethylene Glycol 50% at inlet velocity of 1m/s at 313 K.

The thermal analysis of the serpentine cooling channel using a Aluminium alloy and an ethylene glycol-water mixture (1:1) at an inlet velocity of 1 m/s is demonstrated. From figure 7 the outer cell temperature is approximately 313 K, while the lowest is around 311.5 K.

Figure 6: AA with EG + Water 1:1 at 1m/s

Figure 7: Cooling Curve of Cell with EG + Water 1:1 at 1m/s

Difference of ~1.5 K temperature is the result. As illustrated in figure 8 cooling to around 311.8 K temperature takes 3 minutes to reach at that temperature.

4.3 CASE C: AA with Water at inlet velocity of 3m/s at 313 K.

Figure 8: AA Channel with water as coolant at 3m/s

Figure 9: Cooling Curve of Cell with water at 3m/s

It was illustrated in figure 9 that ~308.5K is the cooling temperature and maximum 4.5K temperature difference is seen in this case at 3m/s inlet velocity. From Fig.10 Cooling curve for Cell temperature is seen in which from 313K to 308.5K decreasing curve is seen. Around 240 seconds temperature is 308.7K.

4.4 CASE D: AA with Water 50% + Ethylene Glycol 50%at inlet velocity of 3m/s at 313 K.

Figure 10: AA with EG + Water 1:1 at 3m/s

Figure 11: Cooling Curve of Cell with EG + Water 1:1 at 3m/s

In this Case D temperature difference result is ~4K and it is clearly seen in the Figure 11. The temperature range is from 313K – 309K. from figure 12 cooling curve it was seen temperature drop from 313K to 309.3K is achieved in 4 minute.

4.5 CASE E: AA with Water at inlet velocity of 5m/s at 313 K

The temperature range observed in this simulation is between 313 K and 306 K. Collant is passed at 5 m/s, and the coolant's outlet temperature is 306 K. Fig.14 shows the cooling curve for a cell in which from 313K to 307K cooling is done within 200 seconds. And this CASE E is the best cooling for Aluminium material

Figure 13 : AA Channel with water as coolant at 5m/s

channel at inlet velocity at 5m/s with water. Cooling temperature difference after 10 minutes is ~ 7K.

Figure 12: Cooling Curve of Cell with water at 5m/s

4.6 CASE F: AA with Water 50% + Ethylene Glycol 50% at inlet velocity of 3m/s at 313 K.

The Simulation results of this Case is having the range from 313K - 306.50K. Temperature difference is ~6.5K as shown in figure 15. And from the figure 16 it was illustrated that from 313K to 307K it take 300 seconds to cool down. Because of ethylene glycol has lower thermal conductivity compare to water this case gave lower compare to CASE E.

Figure 13: AA with EG + Water 1:1 at 5m/s

Figure 14: Cooling Curve of Cell with EG + Water 1:1 at 5m/s

4.7 CASE G: CA with Water at inlet velocity of 1m/s at 313 K.

In CASE G, thermal analysis of a serpentine cooling channel employing a Copper alloy and water at a 1 m/s input velocity is illustrated.

Figure 15 : CA Channel with water as coolant at 1m/s

Figure 16: Cooling Curve of Cell with Water at 1m/s

Figure 17 shows that the outer cell temperature is roughly 313 K, whereas the lowest is around 310 K. The difference in temperature is approximately 3K. As seen in Figure 18, cooling to around 310 K takes 240 seconds.

4.8 CASE H: CA with Water 50% + Ethylene Glycol 50% at inlet velocity of 1m/s at 313 K.

Figure 17: CA with EG + Water 1:1 at 1m/s

Figure 18: Cooling Curve of Cell with EG + Water 1:1 at 1m/s

From the figure 19 it is seen that the Temperature range is from 313K – 310.8K and the temperature difference is ~2.2 K cooling. From figure 20 the cooling curve is seen in which the temperature from 313K to 311K takes 240 seconds to reach.

4.9 CASE I: CA with Water at inlet velocity of 3m/s at 313 K

Figure 19: CA Channel with water as coolant at 3m/s

Figure 20: Cooling Curve of Cell with Water at 3m/s

In CASE I cooling temperature difference is ~ 6K. the simulation temperature range is 313K-307K which is seen in figure 21. From cooling of temperature to 307.20 it takes around 300 seconds to cool down illustrated in figure 22.

4.10 CASE J: CA with Water 50% + Ethylene Glycol 50% at inlet velocity of 3m/s at 313 K.

Figure 21: CA with EG + Water 1:1 at 3m/s

Figure 22: Cooling Curve of Cell with EG + Water 1:1 at 3m/s

As illustrated in figure 23 cooling temperature is from 313K from 307.80K and around 5.2K temperature is decreased. The cooling graph from figure 24 is indicating that 308.2K temperature takes around 180 seconds to cool down. As compared to Case I it is little less efficient.

4.11 CASE K: CA with Water at inlet velocity of 5m/s at 313 K

Figure 23: CA Channel with water as coolant at 5m/s

Figure 24: Cooling Curve of Cell with Water at 5m/s

The result of the decreasing temperature is ~8K of this Case. The temperature is from 313K to 305K as illustrates in figure 25. From all the Cases this case is the best case for the cooling. Within around 240 seconds 305.5K was cooled down from 313K as seen in figure 26.

4.12 CASE L: CA with Water 50% + Ethylene Glycol 50% at inlet velocity of 5m/s at 313 K.

In this last case temperature is range from 313K - 305.5K, and temperature difference is ~7.5K. and the cooling curve is illustrated in Figure 28. Around 306 K temperature is seen after 240 seconds. 0.5K temperature is less compared to Case K.

Figure 25: CA with EG + Water 1:1 at 5m/s

Figure 26: Cooling Curve of Cell with EG + Water 1:1 at 5m/s

4.13 Comparison of All the Cases Graph Results.

Here All the Cooling Curves are Compared as per there different cases in which Case K gave the Best Cooling and Case B is the Worst. Cooling. All the cases are arranged in ascending order as per there Cooling results from higher cooling rate to the lower side.

Figure 27: Cooling Curve Comparison of all the Cases

V. CONCLUSION:

The thermal analysis of a serpentine cooling channel for total 96-cell 18650 battery pack was conducted, with water and Ethylene glycol + Water (1:1) as the coolant and a copper alloy and Aluminium Alloy channel material at 1,3,5 m/s Inlet velocity is conducted. The temperature boundary condition for the cells was set at 313 K. Case K is highly effective Cooling case having CA as channel and water as a coolant. Case B is less effective cooling with EG + water (1:1) at 1m/s. The simulation results indicate

effective heat dissipation across the pack, with a temperature gradient observed along the flow direction. The use of a serpentine cooling strategy demonstrates its potential in enhancing thermal management, ensuring uniform temperature distribution, and preventing hotspots that could degrade battery performance and lifespan. Further optimization of flow rate and channel design may further enhance cooling efficiency.

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